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agricultural soils**

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Yield stability in conventional and organic farming systems: Results from the DOK trial in Switzerland. Report related to EJP SOIL ARTEMIS WP 2

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Abstract

Soils provide multiple ecosystem services that enable a continuous production of crops. Farming systems that promote ecosystem services are also expected to be more resilient against external stressors, enabling a more stable crop production. To better understand the soil-, management- and climatic- related drivers of yield stability in different farming systems, the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project is analysing different long-term field experiments across Europe on these parameters.

This report summarizes the results of the Swiss DOK long-term systems comparison trial in Switzerland. This trial compares conventional and organic farming systems at standard (“full”) or reduced (“half”) fertilizer inputs levels. We used data of a 42-year time series that monitored crop yields, soil properties and climate data over this period. Datasets were split into year of typical climate and years with climatic extremes. Subsequently yield stability indicators of four crops (potatoes, winter wheat, soybean and maize) were calculated. Further, factors affecting these yield stability indicators were determined.

We found that yield stability was generally increased in the conventional farming systems compared to the organic farming system in both years with normal and extreme climate conditions. The largest difference between the farming systems in terms of relative yield stability were observed for the crops potatoes and maize. Soil properties such as soil organic carbon and soil nitrogen concentrations played a minor role in explaining yield fluctuations than actual fertilisation rates and climate variability.

This document is an internal deliverable with the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project that will be further developed into a manuscript for publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

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1. Introduction

Agroecological (AE) systems have gained increasing attention for their potential to deliver important ecosystem services that contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation. However, knowledge about their intermediate- and long-term effectiveness, particularly regarding yield stability under climatic stress, remains limited. Most studies on AE systems stem from field experiments designed to answer agronomic questions related to yield quantities, while the stability of yields has only recently become a focus of research (Macholdt et al., 2020; Schrama et al., 2018). Although it is widely acknowledged that AE systems tend to produce lower yields compared to conventional practices, they may offer higher resilience against extreme climatic events (Lichtfouse, 2012). Despite this, comprehensive analyses of AE systems that focus on their performance during climate extremes, rather than in direct comparison to conventional systems, are still rare.

Climate extremes are complex natural phenomena with a wide range of definitions based on the exposed resource and spatio-temporal extent. The literature displays large inconsistencies regarding the conceptual and operational definition of drought, making it difficult to compare and synthesize results (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010). Defining drought based on the local divergence of climate parameters from long-term normals can considerably reduce the applicability of study outcomes across scales (Slette et al., 2019). The use of standardized drought indices has been suggested as an effective approach to resolve this issue (Chabert & Sarthou, 2020).

Long-term agronomic experiments provide a unique and valuable opportunity to assess long-term effects of different management systems especially on time-dependent metrics such as yield stability, as they provide valuable data sets with long observation periods to account for yearly fluctuations and varying climatic conditions. The DOK long-term farming system comparison trial (DOK) provides a huge opportunity to improve the knowledge of performance trends of different management systems. With now 46 years under practice, it is the world longest-lasting experiment comparing organic and conventional management, providing a unique dataset for analysing long-term effects (Mayer et al., 2015).

This study aims to evaluate differences in yields, yield trends, and yield stability between organic and conventional farming systems. Moreover, this report identifies key factors affecting yields and discusses how yields for both systems are affected during years of climatic stress. We hypothesised that conventional systems would perform better during no environmental pressure (“normal years”), but organic systems might have improved yield stability during adverse climatic conditions due to more resilient and stable soil conditions.

2. Material and Methods

1.1. Experimental Design

The DOK long-term systems comparison trial is located in Therwil, Switzerland (47° 30.158'N, 7° 32.347'E), 308 m above sea level. Average yearly precipitation is 840 mm, and the mean annual temperature is 10.9 °C (climate norm 1991 – 2024). The soil type is a haplic luvisol on deep deposits of alluvial loess. It contains 12% sand, 72% silt, and 16% clay. Eight different treatments corresponding to different management systems and fertilization intensities are compared. In this report, only data of the bioorganic system (BIOORG) and conventional mixed farming system (CONFYMI) at half and full fertilization is included, representative for organic and conventional management respectively. The conventional systems received chemical plant protection, i.e. herbicides, insecticides and fungicides. The pesticides were continuously adapted to the currently recommended preparations. The organic treatments received also crop protection agents, mainly fungicides, insecticides and molluscicides that are approved for use in organic farming, like copper and bacillus thuringiensis preparations. Fertilisation in the conventional system takes place according to the Swiss national recommendations (Sinaj et al., 2017), consisting of farmyard manure that is supplemented with mineral fertiliser to achieve optimal yield. The fertilisation of the organic system is basically reduced to farmyard manure, representing a fertilisation dose equalling 1,4 livestock units.

The experimental design can be described as split-strip-plot with four replicated blocks. The main-plot factor corresponds to three shifted crop rotations (Field A,B,C), where the crop rotation was shifted by one and four years. The horizontal treatment factor is the system (in this report either organic or conventional), and the vertical factor is the fertilization level (half, regular). The trial consists in total of 96 plots with a plot size of 100 m² each. A more detailed description of the experimental design can be found in Oberson et al. (2024).

System		Organic		Conventional	
Fertilization level		Half	Regular	Half	Regular
Average of yearly applied nutrients (kg/ha)	Total N	48	96	86	171
	Mineral N	15	30	57	113
	P	12	24	19	37
	K	92	184	123	248
Organic matter		1016	2032	1157	2314
Farmyard manure & slurry		Manure compost, slurry, equal to 1,4 livestock units		Manure, slurry, equal to 1,4 livestock units	
Mineral fertilization		Rock powder, Potassium sulfate with magnesium		Additional NPK (as recommended)	
Plant protection	Weed control	Mechanical		Mechanical and chemical	
	Disease control	Copper for potatoes		Chemical	
	Pest control	Plant extracts and antagonists		Chemical	
Additional treatments		-		Plant growth regulators	

Table 1 Management of the DOK trial adjusted from Knapp et al. (2023).

2.1. Climate and Climate Scenarios

Climate extremes are complex natural phenomena with a wide range of definitions based on the exposed resource and spatiotemporal extent. The literature displays large inconsistencies regarding the conceptual and operational definition of drought, making it difficult to compare and synthesize results. Defining drought based on the local divergence of climate parameters from long-term normals can considerably reduce the applicability of study outcomes across scales (Dietz et al., 2021; Renwick et al., 2021). The use of standardized drought indices has been suggested by as an effective approach to resolve this issue (Slette et al., 2019; Vihervaara et al., 2013). To assess climate-related effects on yield stability, we chose two climate indices to characterize the climatic stress on crops: Cumulative Dry Days (CDD) and Heat Degree Days (HDD) to include both heat- and drought-related effects on yields. Both indices were calculated crop-specifically for the growing season of each crop to account for differences in growth periods. HDD captures the number of days during the growing season where the temperature exceeds a certain threshold T_{max} . We adjusted the threshold for each crop based on the current literature with $T_{max} > 29^{\circ}$ for potatoes (Roberts et al., 2017), $T_{max} > 28^{\circ}$ for winter wheat (Schauberger et al., 2017), and $T_{max} > 30^{\circ}$ for Soybean and Maize (Lobell et al., 2013; Lüttger & Feike, 2018). CDD reflects periods of prolonged dryness by counting consecutive days with minimal precipitation (see [Figure S1](#) for an overview of the resulting climate indices).

We then performed a clustering analysis per crop using both indices to categorize broadly its degree of climatic stress based on each crop. For that, we employed a 2-means clustering to classify years into two groups (normal years, extreme climatic stress events). The clustering was based on two climate indices: cumulative dry days (CDD) and heat degree days (HDD). CDD measures periods of prolonged drought, while HDD quantifies days with temperatures exceeding 30°C during the growing season. Since the growing season varies by crop, these indices were calculated per crop, making the data crop specific. To prepare for clustering, the CDD and HDD indices were normalized. The k-means algorithm assigns years into two clusters by minimizing the within-cluster variance of CDD and HDD values, effectively grouping similar years based on climate stress. The first cluster represents "normal years" with lower CDD and HDD, while the second cluster groups "extreme climatic years" with higher values for both indices ([Figure 1](#)).

2.2. Mean yields and temporal trend

Treatment means and temporal trends were estimated with the following linear mixed effect model (Model 1) for each crop:

$$YIELD_i \sim T + Y_n + T \times Y_n + RF(F \times Y) \quad (1)$$

where $YIELD_i$ is the mean yield per treatment T and field \times year combination and crop i , Y_n is the numeric year, Y is year used as a factor, F stands for field, and the interaction of $F \times Y$ was used as a random effects structure. Estimated marginal means were calculated using the R-package *emmeans* (Lenth, 2023). Coefficients of the interaction between treatments and year was used as an indicator for treatment-specific temporal trends.

2.3. Yield stability

In the context of agriculture, yield stability is mainly used as a criterion to assess the temporal and spatial invariability of specific features. In this report, we used the variance as a metric for absolute stability (Reckling et al., 2021). As the occurrence of time trends can increase variance estimates, we used the following model (Model 2) to estimate the variance per treatment and crop (Knapp et al., 2023):

$$YIELD_i \sim T + Y_n + T \times Y_n + VS(T, F \times Y) \quad (2)$$

where the random effect structure of model 1 is substituted by a diagonal variance matrix with the diagonal elements representing the absolute stability variances of the treatments as recommended by Piepho (1998).

Relative stability was calculated using the coefficient of variation (CV), which we calculated by dividing the square root of the estimated treatment variances from model 2 by our estimated means of model 1. The CV allows for comparison of yield stability across different treatments (Döring & Reckling, 2018), with lower values indicating more stable yields. For the comparison of yield stability between organic and conventional systems, we performed linear contrasts by calculating the ratio of the coefficients of variation (CV) between treatments. We then calculated for each contrast p-values using z-tests, which allowed us to statistically compare the CVs of organic and conventional systems within each combination of climatic scenario and fertilization level.

2.4. Identification of key factors influencing yields

To identify the key factors influencing crop yields, we applied a Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS) model. This method is particularly suited for capturing nonlinear relationships and interactions between the predictors and the response variable (Friedman, 1991). The input variables included soil properties (pH, organic carbon content, total nitrogen, and key nutrients), fertilization inputs, our two crop-specific climate indices (HDD, CDD), and plant protection activities, characterised simply here as count of activities per treatment and year¹. For each crop, we applied the MARS model using the *earth* package (Millborow et al., 2018) to identify the most important variables influencing yield fluctuations. These variables were ranked based on their contribution to explaining yield variability.

¹ In the subsequent paper, plant protection is going to be analysed in more detail.

Figure 1 Climate Cluster Analysis Overview of the cluster analysis identifying two climatic scenarios ("Normal years" and "Years of climatic stress") based on heat degree days (HDD) and cumulative dry days (CDD). The table shows the yearly HDD and CDD for each crop (potatoes (KA), winter wheat (WW), maize (SM), and soybean (SO)) across the two identified clusters. Cluster 1 ("Normal years") represents years with lower or average climatic stress, while Cluster 2 ("Years of climatic stress") reflects years with high heat and/or drought conditions.

3. Results

3.1. Mean yields

In general, organic systems consistently produced lower yields compared to conventional systems across all crops under normal climate conditions. For potatoes, organic systems yielded 68% of conventional yields at half fertilization and 71% at full fertilization. Winter wheat followed a similar trend, with organic systems producing 86% and 80% of conventional yields at half and full fertilization, respectively. For soybean, the yield difference was smaller, with organic systems reaching 96% and 102% of conventional yields at half and full fertilization. In maize, organic systems achieved 76% and 79% of conventional yields at half and full fertilization, respectively ([Table 2](#)).

When comparing normal and extreme climate conditions, conventional systems generally showed smaller yield reductions compared to organic systems. For potatoes, conventional yields decreased by 8-11%, while organic systems saw slightly higher reductions, especially under half fertilization, where yields dropped to 61% of conventional yields. In contrast, winter wheat yields did not change during years of climatic stress for both systems. Moreover, organic yields in the extreme climate scenario nearly matched or exceeded those of the conventional system, particularly at full fertilization (98% and 96% for half and full fertilization, respectively). For soybean and maize, the climate effect was minimal, with both organic and conventional systems showing relatively stable yields across scenarios. However, organic soybean yields slightly performed better compared to conventional under extreme climate at half fertilization, achieving 103% of conventional yields.

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) of our fixed effects of Model 1 indicated that yield differences are driven mainly by the factor treatment, while the effect of the climate cluster was generally not significant, except for Maize where the interaction between treatment and climatic stress was significant ($p < 0.05$) ([Table 3](#)). This is shown by both conventional and organic systems at full fertilization, where means during climatic stress events even slightly were higher compared to normal years, whereas at half fertilization in both systems yields were lower during the climatic stress years as in all the other crops.

3.2. Yield stability

To assess the effects of conventional and organic farming systems, we calculated linear contrasts of our relative stability measure, characterised in this report as the CV, at different fertilization levels and climatic scenarios. Conventional systems generally were more stable for most crops, with organic systems only being more stable, displayed through a lower CV, at full fertilization within both climatic scenarios ([Figure 2](#)). However, the differences were relatively small and were only statistically significant for winter wheat at half fertilization.

3.3. Soil-related drivers of yields

To identify the most relevant predictors of yields per crop, we used multivariate adaptive regression spline (MARS) models for each crop. This approach allowed us to analyse the effects of different influencing factors, including soil properties (e.g., soil organic carbon and total nitrogen) and other factors such as fertilization inputs and climate variables. Across all crops except soybean, our results showed that fertilization factors, particularly mineral nitrogen (Nmin_fert), and the climate variables had a much larger impact on yield variability for all the crops compared to soil properties ([Table 4](#)).

However, significant effects of some soil properties on yields were found, which varied between the analysed crops. For potatoes, soil organic carbon (SOC) had a significant positive effect on yields up to a threshold of 0.91%. After that, increases in soil organic carbon concentrations did not affect yields any further. Since treatment means of SOC concentrations for ranged between 1.11 % - 1.26%, the threshold of 0.91 % can be interpreted as a critical minimum. Below this level, SOC limitation may occur, resulting in significantly lower yields. For maize, SOC contributed beyond a threshold of 1.04%. For winter wheat, total soil nitrogen (Ntot_soil) played the largest role for predicting yields after a minimum concentration of 0.139% ([Figure 3](#)). However, further analysis is required to corroborate these findings.

Crop	Treatment	Fert. Level	Climate Cluster	Yields		Relative Differences	
				Est. Means (t ha ⁻¹)	SE (t ha ⁻¹)	System (%)	Climate (%)
Potatoes (n=15)	Conventional	half	1	9.07	0.54	-	-
			2	8.30	1.09	-	92%
		full	1	10.84	0.54	-	-
			2	9.65	1.09	-	89%
	Organic	half	1	6.14	0.54	68%	-
			2	5.06	1.09	61%	82%
		full	1	7.66	0.54	71%	-
			2	6.75	1.09	70%	88%
Winter wheat (n=30)	Conventional	half	1	17.41	0.69	-	-
			2	17.84	1.31	-	102%
		full	1	19.28	0.69	-	-
			2	20.07	1.31	-	104%
	Organic	half	1	14.89	0.69	86%	-
			2	17.20	1.31	96%	116%
		full	1	15.45	0.69	80%	-
			2	19.73	1.31	98%	128%
Soybean (n=9)	Conventional	half	1	2.66	0.10	-	-
			2	2.57	0.19	-	97%
		full	1	2.78	0.10	-	-
			2	3.09	0.19	-	111%
	Organic	half	1	2.55	0.10	96%	-
			2	2.64	0.19	103%	104%
		full	1	2.84	0.10	102%	-
			2	2.77	0.19	89%	97%
Maize (n=9)	Conventional	half	1	4.77	0.18	-	-
			2	4.68	0.19	-	98%
		full	1	5.06	0.18	-	-
			2	5.08	0.19	-	101%
	Organic	half	1	3.62	0.18	76%	-
			2	3.55	0.19	76%	98%
		full	1	4.01	0.18	79%	-
			2	4.03	0.19	79%	101%

Table 2 Estimated treatment yield means within different climatic scenarios and fertilization levels. Treatment means, and their respective standard errors (SE) estimated by linear mixed effect models separately for four different crops for years with either normal climate (1) or during years of climatic stress (2). Climate scenarios were compiled by a 2-means clustering analysis per crop using a crop-specific heat-related and drought-related climate index calculated for the whole growing season. System gap is defined as the percentage of mean yield in organic farming system over those in conventional farming system per crop, fertilisation level and climate cluster. Climate gap is defined as the percentage of mean yield in year with climatic stress over years with normal climate per crop, fertilisation level and farming system.

	KA		WW		SM		SO	
	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
(Intercept)	347.48	0.00	1381.92	0.00	992.53	0.00	1510.44	0.00
treat	77.81	0.00	125.31	0.00	31.50	0.00	4.30	0.01
climate	0.99	0.34	0.00	0.98	1.43	0.28	0.22	0.66
year	0.79	0.39	1.17	0.29	1.89	0.22	2.33	0.18
treat:year	0.30	0.82	5.59	0.00	0.47	0.71	0.35	0.79
trat:climate	0.11	0.95	0.27	0.84	5.31	0.00	1.35	0.27

Table 3: ANOVA of fixed effects separated by crop. Overview of an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) assessing the effects of treatment, climate cluster (normal vs. climatic stress), time trend (numeric year), and their interactions on yields for Potatoes (KA), Winter Wheat (WW), Maize (SM), and Soybean (SO). The table shows *F-values*, and corresponding *p-values* for each fixed effect and interaction term in each linear mixed effect models.

Figure 2 Comparison of relative stability ratios between organic and conventional systems with either half (1, left) or normal (2, right) fertilization application. The plots illustrate the coefficient of variation (CV) for organic systems divided by the CV for conventional systems in either years with normal climate (A; above) or during years of higher climatic stress (B; bottom) for crops of potatoes (KA), Winter Wheat (WW), Soybean (SO), and Maize (SM). The black dashed line at $x = 1$ indicates equal relative stability between organic and conventional systems. Error margins are based on the SE of the CV, with p -values displayed for each crop, showing the statistical significance of the comparison.

Category	Variable	KA		WW		SM		SO	
		nsubsets	gcv	nsubsets	gcv	nsubsets	gcv	nsubsets	gcv
Soil properties	pH_soil	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Corg_soil	9	17.2	-	-	4	26	-	-
	Ntot_soil	-	-	2	11	-	-	-	-
	P_soil	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	K_soil	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	53.7
	Mg_soil	-	-	9	24.8	7	32.4	-	-
Nutrient Inputs	N_fert	-	-	-	-	12	100	-	-
	Nmin_fert	21	100	21	100	-	-	-	-
	P_fert	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	K_fert	4	12.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Ca_fert	1	10.4	10	29	6	30.6	-	-
	Mg_fert	16	48.9	-	-	6	28.3	-	-
Climate	S_fert	13	45.2	15	49.3	2	13.7	-	-
	CDD	18	70.2	20	79.1	11	80.3	3	100
Plant Protection	HDD	17	70.9	18	65.3	10	72.3	-	-
	count_PP	12	40.4	16	55.2	9	62.7	-	-

Table 4: Yield predictors selected by multivariate adaptive splines models per crop. Overview of all selected variables influencing crop yields by the Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS) model for potatoes (KA), Winter wheat (WW), Maize (SM), and Soybean (SO). The variables are grouped into soil properties, fertilization, climate indices, and plant protection. The columns show the number of subsets each variable was included, and their relative importance based on the Generalized Cross-Validation (gcv).

Figure 3 Partial dependence plots for selected soil-related predictors of yields (1) and boxplots (2) for potatoes (A), winter wheat (B), and maize (C). Relevant partial dependences of soil properties to yield fluctuations selected by multivariate adaptive regression splines models per crop. Soil properties are expressed in % and yields in t ha⁻¹.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

We analysed a long-term data series (42 years) of a long-term field experiment located in Switzerland that compares organic farming and conventional farming systems at standard and halved fertilisation rates. Our findings demonstrate that conventional systems consistently perform better compared to organic systems in terms of yield stability, especially at half fertilization, across most crops. A similar pattern is apparent for yields that are higher in the conventional systems under normal climate conditions, where organic yields for potatoes, maize, and winter wheat were generally lower, achieving only 68-86% of conventional yields ([Table 2](#)). This yield gap between conventional and organic systems is well reported in the literature (Ahmed Waqas et al., 2020; Knapp & van der Heijden, 2018; Li et al., 2019; Schrama et al., 2018). In our case, the main factor can be attributed to differences in synthetic inputs, especially mineral nitrogen as seen in [Table 4](#), which likely provided more consistent nutrient availability and thus increased yields. In terms of yield stability, conventional systems exhibited greater yield stability for most crops, with the only significant advantage for organic systems being observed at full fertilization at soybean in both climate scenarios ([Figure 2](#)). This suggests that organic systems mainly can close the yield gap in scenarios when nutrient limitations are less severe (Li et al., 2019).

Climatic conditions had varying effects on both systems, but conventional systems generally demonstrated better resilience to climatic stress. For potatoes, conventional systems experienced only a small reduction in yield (8-11%) under climatic stress, whereas organic systems showed a more pronounced decline, especially under half fertilization (a drop to 61% of conventional yields). This indicates that conventional systems might be more resilient against environmental stress due to more robust nutrient management practices as also observed in (Montgomery & Bikié, 2021). Interestingly, winter wheat yields were unaffected by climatic stress, regardless of the system, with organic yields even outperforming conventional ones in some cases (98% of conventional yields during stress events) ([Table 2](#)). This may suggest that winter wheat is more resilient to climate fluctuations or that organic management practices favour winter wheat under stress conditions. In contrast, soybean and maize yields were stable under climatic stress for both systems, with only minor differences in performance, and organic soybean outperformed conventional at half fertilization under extreme conditions (103%).

Despite our findings, there are several limitations to this study. One major limitation is the relatively small number of observations with climatic stress events, especially for maize and soybean. The limited data for these crops under extreme climate scenarios restricts our findings about their long-term stability under stress. Another key limitation is the incomplete evaluation of plant protection measures. Given that plant protection practices differ greatly between organic and conventional systems, with conventional systems relying more on synthetic pesticides, this could have a significant impact on yield stability and is currently investigated in detail.

5. Supplementary Tables and Figures

Figure S1 Heat maps of climate indices over experimental years. Heatmaps displaying heat degree days (HDD) and cumulative dry days (CDD) across experimental years for four crops: potatoes (KA), winter wheat (WW), maize (SM), and soybean (SO). The heat maps are color-coded, with five intensity levels to represent the range of climate stress experienced during the growing season. For HDD, darker shades of red indicate higher temperatures, while for CDD, darker shades of blue indicate prolonged dry periods.

6. References

- Ahmed Waqas, M., Smith, P., Wang, X., Nadeem Ashraf, M., Ali Noor, M., Amou, M., Shi, S., Zhu, Y., Li, J., Wan, Y., Qin, X., Gao, Q., & Liu, S. (2020). *The influence of nutrient management on soil organic carbon storage, crop production, and yield stability varies under different climates*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121922>
- Chabert, A., & Sarthou, J.-P. (2020). Conservation agriculture as a promising trade-off between conventional and organic agriculture in bundling ecosystem services. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 292, 106815. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.106815>
- Dietz, K. -J., Zörb, C., & Geilfus, C. -M. (2021). Drought and crop yield. *Plant Biology*, 23(6), 881–893. <https://doi.org/10.1111/plb.13304>
- Döring, T. F., & Reckling, M. (2018). Detecting global trends of cereal yield stability by adjusting the coefficient of variation. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 99, 30–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2018.06.007>
- Friedman, J. H. (1991). Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines. *The Annals of Statistics*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.1214/aos/1176347963>
- Knapp, S., Gunst, L., Mäder, P., Ghiasi, S., & Mayer, J. (2023). Organic cropping systems maintain yields but have lower yield levels and yield stability than conventional systems – Results from the DOK trial in Switzerland. *Field Crops Research*, 302, 109072. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2023.109072>
- Knapp, S., & van der Heijden, M. G. A. (2018). A global meta-analysis of yield stability in organic and conservation agriculture. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 3632. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05956-1>
- Lenth, R. V. (2023). *Estimated Marginal Means, aka Least-Squares Means* (R package version 1.8.6). <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=emmeans>
- Li, M., Peterson, C. A., Tautges, N. E., Scow, K. M., & Gaudin, A. C. M. (2019). Yields and resilience outcomes of organic, cover crop, and conventional practices in a Mediterranean climate. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 12283. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-48747-4>
- Lichtfouse, E. (2012). *Agroecology and Strategies for Climate Change*. Springer Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-1905-7>
- Lobell, D. B., Hammer, G. L., McLean, G., Messina, C., Roberts, M. J., & Schlenker, W. (2013). The critical role of extreme heat for maize production in the United States. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(5), 497–501. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1832>
- Lüttger, A. B., & Feike, T. (2018). Development of heat and drought related extreme weather events and their effect on winter wheat yields in Germany. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 132(1–2), 15–29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-017-2076-y>
- Macholdt, J., Styczen, M. E., Macdonald, A., Piepho, H.-P., & Honermeier, B. (2020). Long-term analysis from a cropping system perspective: Yield stability, environmental adaptability, and production risk of winter barley. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 117, 126056. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2020.126056>
- Mayer, J., Gunst, L., Mäder, P., Samson, M.-F., Carcea, M., Narducci, V., Thomsen, I. K., & Dubois, D. (2015). “Productivity, quality and sustainability of winter wheat under long-term conventional

and organic management in Switzerland." *European Journal of Agronomy*, 65, 27–39.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2015.01.002>

- Milborrow, S., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (2018). earth: Multivariate adaptive regression splines; 2021. URL <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=earth>. *R package version*, 5(1).
- Montgomery, D. R., & Biklé, A. (2021). Soil Health and Nutrient Density: Beyond Organic vs. Conventional Farming. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.699147>
- Oberson, A., Jarosch, K. A., Frossard, E., Hammelehle, A., Fließbach, A., Mäder, P., & Mayer, J. (2024). Higher than expected: Nitrogen flows, budgets, and use efficiencies over 35 years of organic and conventional cropping. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 362, 108802.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108802>
- Piepho, H. -P. (1998). Methods for Comparing the Yield Stability of Cropping Systems. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science*, 180(4), 193–213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-037X.1998.tb00526.x>
- Reckling, M., Ahrends, H., Chen, T.-W., Eugster, W., Hadasch, S., Knapp, S., Laidig, F., Linstädter, A., Macholdt, J., Piepho, H.-P., Schiffers, K., & Döring, T. F. (2021). Methods of yield stability analysis in long-term field experiments. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 41(2), 27.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-021-00681-4>
- Renwick, L. L. R., Deen, W., Silva, L., Gilbert, M. E., Maxwell, T., Bowles, T. M., & Gaudin, A. C. M. (2021). Long-term crop rotation diversification enhances maize drought resistance through soil organic matter. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(8), 084067. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac1468>
- Roberts, M. J., Braun, N. O., Sinclair, T. R., Lobell, D. B., & Schlenker, W. (2017). Comparing and combining process-based crop models and statistical models with some implications for climate change. *Environmental Research Letters*, 12(9), 095010. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa7f33>
- Schauberger, B., Archontoulis, S., Arneth, A., Balkovic, J., Ciais, P., Deryng, D., Elliott, J., Folberth, C., Khabarov, N., Müller, C., Pugh, T. A. M., Rolinski, S., Schaphoff, S., Schmid, E., Wang, X., Schlenker, W., & Frieler, K. (2017). Consistent negative response of US crops to high temperatures in observations and crop models. *Nature Communications*, 8(1), 13931.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms13931>
- Schrama, M., de Haan, J. J., Kroonen, M., Verstegen, H., & Van der Putten, W. H. (2018). Crop yield gap and stability in organic and conventional farming systems. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 256, 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.12.023>
- Sinaj, S., Charles, R., Baux, A., Dupuis, B., Hiltbrunner, J., Levy, L., Pellet, D., Blanchet, G., & Jeangros, B. (2017). Düngung von Ackerkulturen. In W. Richner & S. Sinaj (Eds.), *Grundlagen für die Düngung landwirtschaftlicher Kulturen in der Schweiz (GRUD 2017)* (pp. 1–46). Agroscope.
- Slette, I. J., Post, A. K., Awad, M., Even, T., Punzalan, A., Williams, S., Smith, M. D., & Knapp, A. K. (2019). How ecologists define drought, and why we should do better. *Global Change Biology*, 25(10), 3193–3200. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14747>

Vicente-Serrano, S. M., Beguería, S., & López-Moreno, J. I. (2010). A Multiscalar Drought Index Sensitive to Global Warming: The Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index. *Journal of Climate*, 23(7), 1696–1718. <https://doi.org/10.1175/2009JCLI2909.1>

Vihervaara, P., D'Amato, D., Forsius, M., Angelstam, P., Baessler, C., Balvanera, P., Boldgiv, B., Bourgeron, P., Dick, J., Kanka, R., Klotz, S., Maass, M., Melecis, V., Petřík, P., Shibata, H., Tang, J., Thompson, J., & Zacharias, S. (2013). Using long-term ecosystem service and biodiversity data to study the impacts and adaptation options in response to climate change: insights from the global ILTER sites network. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 5(1), 53–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2012.11.002>